

Spectrophotometric Determination of Selenium (IV) with Acetothioacetanilide

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Manuscript received 22 July 1977, revised 7 February 1979, accepted 6 June 1979

Small quantities (0.05-100 ppm) of selenium(IV) has been extracted into chloroform as the 1:2-complex with acetothioacetanilide from solutions of pH 0.3-0.7 containing phosphoric acid. The absorbance of the orange-yellow complex has been measured at 400 nm against reagent blank 150 minutes after extraction. The determination is possible with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.24\%$. The colour of the complex is stable up to 3 days and sufficient amounts of Hg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , AsO_4^{3-} , Fe^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Be^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , In^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Th^{4+} , MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , Te^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} were tolerated. The estimation is not possible in the presence of Ag^+ , Pt^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Au^{3+} ions.

GENERALLY selenium is determined by the reduction of selenium(IV) and selenium(VI) or the measurement of absorbance of the piazoselenols formed between selenous acid and aromatic *o*-diamines¹. The reduction processes are time consuming, laborious and mostly insensitive. Photometric estimation of selenium includes 3-3'-diaminobenzidine², mercaptobenzothiazole³ and N-N'-bis-(β -benzoyl-ethyl)-*o*-phenylenediamines⁴ but the interference due to other elements, particularly tellurium renders most of the reagents to be of limited use. The methods using 1,4-diphenylthiosemicarbazide⁵ and mercaptobenzothiazole are of poor accuracy. Only Nazaranko, Kislov and Kislova's method using 2,3-diaminonaphthane⁶ seems to have good selectivity.

A method for the determination of selenium with acetothioacetanilide has been developed. This method has higher selectivity than that of 2,3-diaminonaphthane while the accuracy is comparable to it. The sensitivity is also high and very small quantities of selenium, 100 μg of selenium(IV), per ml of chloroform has been determined.

Experimental

Acetothioacetanilide Solution: Thiodiacetothioacetanilide was prepared in the laboratory following a standard method⁷ from acetylacetone and phenylisothioyanate in dry ether. The product on hydrolysis produced acetothioacetanilide which was crystallised twice from 40% aqueous ethanol.

A total of 2.0-2.5 ml of 0.6-1.0% solution (0.035 to 0.06M) of the reagent in 40% aqueous ethanol was required for each determination. Fresh solutions were used as the solutions on long standing in the presence of light slowly polymerised in a few days.

Selenium(IV) Solution: Pure elemental selenium (E. Merck) was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and the solution was neutralised with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The selenium content was determined as element using hydroxylamine hydrochloride⁸. The solution was diluted so that the final concentration was 0.20 mg per ml.

Phosphoric Acid Solution: A stock solution was prepared by diluting 20 ml of concentrated phosphoric acid (analytical grade) to 100 ml with water. For each extraction 10 ml of this solution was used.

Diverse Ion Solutions: Stock solutions of diverse metal ions were prepared from sulphates, chlorides or nitrates of various metals.

Apparatus: Absorbance was measured in a Hilger and Watts H700 Uvispek Spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cuvettes and the pH meter used was a Cambridge one (fench model).

Procedure for Selenium(IV): Take a known volume (0.5-5 ml) of the stock selenium solution containing 0.1-1.0 mg of it, dilute to 10-15 ml with diluted phosphoric acid solution to adjust the pH between 0.3 and 0.7 before adding 2 ml of the reagent solution. Shake the mixture for 5 minutes while yellow orange colour of the complex develops. Extract the complex twice with 5 ml batches of chloroform. Transfer the combined organic layer into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dehydrate with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Measure the absorbance at 400 nm after 2½ hrs against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance Curve and Beer's Law: The absorbance values of several extracts containing 10-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of selenium(IV) against wave length were recorded in the range 350-450 nm. In all

cases reagent blanks was used as reference. The relevant portion of the plots (Fig. 1) showed that the selenium(IV) complex has a λ_{\max} at 400 nm, while the reagent curve shows a peak at 370 nm. Still a reagent blank was necessary. Beer's law was found to be valid until a maximum concentration of selenium(IV) of 100 μg per ml was reached.

Fig. 1. Absorption curve of Se(IV) Acetothioacetanilide.

[A] = 0.01 mg/ml
[B] = 0.02 mg/ml
[C] = 0.03 mg/ml
[D] = 0.04 mg/ml
[E] = Reagent Blank.

Selection of Extracting Solvent and Stability of the Complex :

Chloroform was found to be the most suitable solvent due to the ease in extraction and stability of the complex. The complex was recovered to the extent of about 95% in the first step while the second extraction made the process quantitative. The extent of extraction of the complex in isoamyl alcohol or isobutylmethylketone was very low and almost nil in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide.

The maximum intensity of the chloroform extract was reached after 150 minutes and this remained unchanged even after 3 days.

Effect of pH and Reagent Concentration :

The absorbance values indicated that extraction was complete only when the pH was in between 0.3 and 0.7.

Experiments using 5 to 25 ml of the reagent for each extraction showed that 10-12 mg of it was

required for the quantitative extraction of 0.05 to 1.0 mg of selenium(IV) present in aqueous medium.

The Nature of the Complex : A small amount of the red selenium acetothioacetanilide complex was precipitated at the same pH used for extraction. The elemental analysis for nitrogen, sulphur and selenium were carried out respectively by Dumas' method, sulphate method and by reduction to elemental selenium. The results, Se, found 16.98% (calc. 17.06%), N, found 5.92% (calc. 6.04%) and S, found 13.80% (calc. 13.82%) indicated the ratio of selenium to the ligand in the complex as 1 : 2.

Some solid complex was mixed with aluminium oxide and subjected to heating at the rate of 12° per minute in a Metriplex photorecording Derivatograph Model OD 102 (Hungary). The complex decomposed exothermally at 320° and the decomposition was complete with a loss of 100% in weight at 960°. An inflation at 660° indicated the temperature of volatilisation of selenium. The loss in weight agreed when the complex was assumed to have metal ligand in the ratio 1 : 2.

The composition of selenium(IV) acetothioacetanilide complex in solution was further verified by the conventional slope-ratio method. In this method metal-ligand ratio was observed as 1 : 2.

Though the precipitation of selenium(IV) by acetothioacetanilide was quantitative it could not be developed into a satisfactory gravimetric procedure as the precipitate was sticky in nature.

Effect of Diverse Ion : One of the advantages of this method lies in the fact that even 20 mg of Te(IV) does not interfere. The tolerance limits for other diverse ions studied, Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , AsO_3^{3-} , UO_2^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Th^{4+} , WO_4^{2-} , Be^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , In^{3+} , MoO_4^{2-} , Te^{4+} are high. Among these, Pb^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , are removed by filtration as their phosphates before extraction. However a little excess of phosphoric acid (3 ml) is required in the presence of Fe^{3+} . Determination of selenium(IV) in the presence of Ag^+ , Pd^{2+} or Pt^{2+} is not possible. Also Ce(IV) oxidises the reagent in the acidic condition in which Se(IV) is determined. The results are presented in Table 1.

Optimum Concentration Range and Sensitivity :

The optimum concentration^o range was 8-30 ppm of selenium in chloroform. Sandell sensitivity^o was 0.04 ppm while the practical sensitivity was 0.4 ppm. Molar absorptivity and standard deviation were found to be 2078 at 400 nm and $\pm 0.24\%$ respectively. The confidence interval was 20.24 ± 0.09 ppm, i.e., from 20.15 to 20.33 ppm for 95% confidence limit. The value of standard

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Se(IV) IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS, Se TAKEN - 20 µg/ml.

Diverse ions (mg)	Absorbance	Se,IV) found (µg)	Rel. error (%)
Hg ²⁺ , 30	0.54, 0.525	21.0, 20.3	+5.0, +1.5
Cd ²⁺ , 10	0.53, 0.52	20.5, 20.0	+2.5, nil
Cu ²⁺ , 10	0.53, 0.528	20.5, 20.4	+2.5, +2.0
Ni ²⁺ , 10	0.53, 0.53	20.5, 20.5	+2.5, +2.5
Co ²⁺ , 10	0.54, 0.53	21.0, 20.5	+5.0, +2.5
AsO ₄ ³⁻ , 30	0.52, 0.517	20.0, 19.8	nil, -1.0
Fe ²⁺ , 10	0.53, 0.53	20.5, 20.5	+2.5, +2.5
Al ³⁺ , 20	0.54, 0.528	20.0, 20.4	nil, +2.0
Bi ³⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.52	20.0, 20.0	nil, nil
Be ²⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.53	20.0, 20.5	nil, +2.5
Mn ²⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.517	20.0, 19.8	nil, -1.0
In ³⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.52	20.0, 20.0	nil, nil
Mg ²⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.52	20.0, 20.0	nil, nil
Pb ²⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.52	20.0, 20.0	nil, nil
ZrO ₂ ²⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.52	20.0, 20.0	nil, nil
Zn ²⁺ , 25	0.52, 0.52	20.0, 20.0	nil, nil
Th ⁴⁺ , 30	0.52, 0.53	20.0, 20.5	nil, +2.5
MoO ₄ ²⁻ , 30	0.53, 0.52	20.5, 20.0	+2.5, nil
WO ₄ ²⁻ , 30	0.52, 0.53	20.0, 20.5	nil, +2.5
UO ₂ ²⁺ , 5	0.538, 0.53	20.4, 20.5	+2.0, +2.5
Ta ⁵⁺ , 30	0.528, 0.52	20.4, 20.0	+2.0, nil

deviation was obtained from measurement of absorbance for aliquots taken from the same stock solution of selenium¹⁰ and the confidence limit was calculated using statistical table¹¹.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Government of

India for awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to T.P.

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